

Eco-taxonomic profile and mtDNA barcode of *Metaphire megascolidioides* (Goto & Hatai, 1899) – a megadrile earthworm from Japan, plus miscellaneous taxonomic mending.

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Abstract

Metaphire megascolidioides (Goto & Hatai, 1899), distributed throughout Japan and possibly introduced to Korea, is redescribed and appended with its mtDNA barcode & phylogeny as obtained for the first time. Molecular indication is for Kyushu specimens requiring separate specific status and thus Korean conspecificity is now also suspect.

Issues concerning final resolution of alternate *Amyntas/Amyntas/Amyntas* spelling – and its priority over attempted restoration of *Pheretima* – plus determination of male pores of *Amyntas/Metaphire* are fully discussed and firmly resolved.

Heteroprorodrilus tryoni (Fletcher, 1890) from Samford, Qld gives the first mtDNA barcode sequence ID for this group of Australian (and Indian?) “Plutelloids” (Plutellinae); cf. Argilophilinae from North America. South American acanthodrilid *Microscolex dubius* (Fletcher, 1887) was a new Asian record and ocnerodrilid *Eukerria saltensis* (Beddard, 1895) a new Japanese record – both species collected by the author and seemingly sequenced for the first time (no BLAST matches). Pontodrilid *Pontodrilus litoralis* (Grube, 1855) is a new record from the Philippines. North American lumbricid *Bimastos parvus* (Eisen, 1874) is a new Okinawan record. The current study also unearthed a new record from Mishima-shi of aquatic, cosmopolitan microdrile Lumbriculidae type *Lumbriculus variegatus* (Müller, 1774).

Correct family separation of Acanthodrilidae *s. mihi* (Blakemore, 2000; 2013), from Ocnerodrilidae, Octochaetidae, Benhamiidae, Exxidae & Megascolecidae *s. stricto* is restated with support of taxonomy, geography, morphology & DNA phylogeny.

INTRODUCTION

Just ten Japanese pheretimoid earthworms were known from Japan when Professor Sietaro Goto (五島清太郎) and his assistant Shinkichi Hatai (畑井新喜司) gave names to ca. 27 ‘new’ pheretimoid species, with descriptions so inadequate and/or confused that most quickly went directly into synonymy or *incertae sedis* in Michaelsen (1899; 1900) or, at best, as *species inquirendae* in Michaelsen (1903: 85) – see Blakemore (2003; 2012a: tabs. 1, 2). Even after 110 years several taxa still remain problematic. Yet all such issues could have been rapidly solved with reference to original type specimens, if these had been made available in good time.

Only in 2010 was a box of Goto & Hatai’s earthworm types finally discovered (Blakemore & Ueshima, 2011; Blakemore, 2012a) in the laboratory of Dr Eijiro Nishi of Yokohama National University (YNU). This crucial, heritage earthworm collection (ca. 40 lots) had been on loan from The University Museum, University of Tokyo (Todai UMUTZ) to a Mr Kotaro Ishizuka from as long before as 1981 (Fig. 1). Perhaps even earlier as Easton (1979: 43) remarked that Dr M. Imajima reported to

him that the “holotype” of *Polypheretima iizukai* (Goto & Hatai, 1899) [= *Amyntas fuscatus* (Goto & Hatai, 1898)], at one time in the Todai collection, was no longer located there.

Fig. 1. Box of historical Tokyo University earthworms as fortunately rediscovered in 2010 – lost for 110 years with 30 years absence! – labelled: “[To] Dr Eijiro Nishi, Original earthworm samples, Heisei 13, 7 month [July, 2001]. [From] Mr Kotaro Ishizuka (石塚小太郎)” that contained 40 heritage jars, some as shown, of Goto & Hatai’s classical types for some reason secreted in a corner of a room at Dr Nishi’s lab in Yokohama. A summary report is in APPENDIX 2.

When I inspected these neglected, historical samples, most of the glass jars were original, but some were cracked and the labels and contents were in various states of deterioration and leakage (see Fig. 1) which is an inexcusable and unforgivable shame as these samples must have survived, due to the diligence of earlier curators who recognized their value, both the 1923 Great Kanto Earthquake and the 1940’s US carpet fire-bombing of Tokyo. Moreover, after I arranged their safe return to UMUTZ courtesy of Dr Rei Ueshima, they again survived the ‘Eastern Japan Great Earthquake’ and Fukushima nuclear meltdown of 11th March, 2011.

On his return to Sendai, Japan from the USA in 1920s, Dr S. Hatai unrepentantly continued his studies on earthworms. Again important specimens – including more of his vital types – were seemingly loaned out and remained hidden for several decades until they too were located, by chance, under auspices of senior scientific curator Dr Toshiaki Kuramochi of National Science Museum, Tokyo (NSMT), and these were curated and reported on by Blakemore (2012a) (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Another unregistered box of earthworms – also including types – relocated in Tokyo NMST in 2010 with label that translates as: “1981 (Showa 61), October, 10th. Transferred from Saito Ho-on Kai Museum [in Sendai]. Imajima & Ishizuka (石塚小太郎). *Oligochaeta Pheretima* group (フトミミズ futo mimizu)”.

It is possible that the syntype of *M. megascolidioides* was in either of these two discarded heritage-collection boxes, but unfortunately this cannot now be determined due to negligence and the subsequent passage of time (see Appendix 2). Nevertheless, it is one of the few Goto & Hatai species that is almost unequivocal due to its male pores displaced to segment 19 rather than on 18 (or aborted) as is more usual for megascolecids. Such a feature is not unique though, being also found, for example, in *Metaphire isselii* (Cognetti, 1908), *Amyntas infantilis* (Chen, 1938), *A. cruratus* (Chen, 1946) and cosmopolitan Indo-Chinese *M. anomala* (Michaelsen, 1907) the latter having its male pores on segment 20 (see Blakemore, 2002; 2016b).

Redescription of the taxon of our specific concern follows.

METHODS

The species's eco-taxonomic description is herein augmented with the author's sketch and DNA barcodes obtained in 2010 using conventions and methodologies of Blakemore (2000; 2016b). Taxonomic remarks on correct generic placement are in the Discussion while DNA data and analysis of this and several other taxa are presented in Appendix 1. Species, genus and family allocations are reconfirmed.

RESULTS - Eco-taxonomic Description

Metaphire megascolidioides (Goto & Hatai, 1899)

Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. *Metaphire megascolidioides* Nogeyama specimen (coll.: RJB & T.J. Tansey, 3.XII.2011) compared to Goto & Hatai's (1899: fig. 16); DNA data in Appendix 1.

Synonymy:

Perichaeta megascolidioides Goto & Hatai, 1899: 21, 24, fig. 16; Hatai, 1922: 333; 1924: 23.

Amyntas megascolidioides : Beddard, 1900: 622.

Pheretima megascolidioides : Michaelsen, [1900](#): 283; 1903: 97; Song & Paik, 1971: 193; Ishizuka, 2001: 94, figs, 1-10 (figures inadvertently inverted!); Minamiya *et al.*, [2007](#): 56; [2009](#): 15; [2012](#): 6.

Amyntas megascolidioides : Sims & Easton, 1972: 236; Easton, 1981: 54.

Metaphire megascolidioides : Blakemore, 2003: 243; 2008: 123; 2010: 203; 2012a: 97; 2012b: 19; Minamiya, [2016](#).

Note: Sometimes misspelt: “*megascolidioides*”, “*megascolidioides*” or “*megascolidioides*”.

Diagnosis: In life, darkish pinky brown with white clitellum on 14-16 or light grey in alcohol with darker clitellum. Length up to 260 mm by about 15 mm width. Segments up to about 130. Setae number up to about 50 per segment. Dorsal pores from 12/13. Spermathecal pores in 4/5/6/7/8/9. Male pores in slight copulatory pouches on segment 19. Genital markings small paired in line with male pores on 17, 18, 20 and sometimes 21,22 (although one Korean specimen had an extra marking on 23). Septa 8/9/10 aborted around muscular gizzard. Holandric (metandric?); seminal vesicles in 11 & 12. Ovaries in 13. Last hearts in 13. Intestine from around 15; intestinal caeca manicate main sac with additional appendages (= multiple). Gut contains soil and a few grits.

Ecology and behaviour: Sluggish to handle if found on surface when stranded after nocturnal wandering. Under Masanobu Fukoka-style natural farming (i.e., no tillage and weed mulch management) this species was reported to be co-dominant with *Eisenia japonica* (Michaelsen, 1892) after 5 years at a site in Akame, Mie in Japan by Arai *et al.* (2014). These authors classed it as “anecic” which implies it feeds at the surface but lives deep in the soil; however the gut content is mainly soil (pers. obs.) indicating subsoil geophagy. At Noge-yama many surface casts were found and associated specimens were wandering on the ground after rain along with *Amyntas masatakae* (Beddard, 1892) – see Blakemore ([2012](#)); Blakemore & Lee ([2013](#)). Hatai (1922, 1924) reported on moisture content and other characters of this worm.

Material examined; DNA and habitats: Type from compound of the then Central Meteorological Observatory Akasaka, Tokyo; missing and possibly borrowed from Todai Museum Collection? Still occurring in Tokyo, e.g. in the Imperial Palace grounds, but not found on Todai Ueno campus (pers. obs.), this species is particularly common in parklands around Kamakura including Kotokuin (Daibutsu) Temple (RJB, 2002 & 12th June, 2006). From Nara and Kii Peninsula (Sakai, Blakemore *et al.* 2006). Collected from survey of rice fields and satoyama forest at Kurozu, Lake Biwa, Shiga-ken, RJB 17th June, 2009, specimens in Biwako Museum (LBM FY2009-13/FY2010-22-5/6 providing DNA JET-178-179 tissue samples send to iBOL with results available in Appendix); Noge-yama, Yokohama specimens collected after rain, RJB + T.J. Tansy; 3.XII.2011, deposited in NIBR, Incheon: mature IV250896, immature IV250997 (DNA sample WO37 failed in Korean polychaete lab.).

Distribution: Japan, from Hokkaido (see Appendix) to Kyushu and Tsushima (Kobayashi, 1941); also Mt Jiri, Korea (Song & Paik, 1971); although molecular indication is for specimens from Kyushu requiring separate specific status and Korean conspecificity may now also be suspect (see BLAST/phylogeny results in Appendix 1).

DISCUSSION

Remarks concerning *Metaphire megascolidioides*

Michaelsen (1900) repeated Goto & Hatai's statement that the intestinal caeca were paired, thus Easton (1981) had them as simple; whereas inspection of newly collected material confirms them as manicate/multiple (Fig. 3). These, plus five pairs of spermathecae and male pores on 19 are characteristic. The male pores are on the tips of small eversible penes that are usually withdrawn in copulatory pouches (pers. obs.), as for genus-type *Metaphire californica* (Kinberg, 1867) and thereby qualifying this taxon for inclusion in *Metaphire* as per Blakemore (2003). It is worrying that the original authors had only a single specimen and could not distinguish its manicate caeca, thus casting into doubt some of their other descriptions; nor did Hatai correct such mistakes.

The syntype was not found in National Museum collections (Blakemore, 2012a; Blakemore & Ueshima, 2012) but, because there is no exceptional need at the moment, a topotypic neotype is not required under ICZN (1999) cf. Blakemore *et al.* (2010). However, in order to determine true relationship of Tokyo specimens with those from Kyushu, Tsushima and Korea, such defining types may eventually be required.

Regarding resolution of *Amynthas/Amyntas/Amythas* and restoration of *Pheretima*

Several willful attempts for restoration of *Pheretima* Kinberg, 1867: 97 in preference to both *Amynthas* Kinberg, 1867: 97 and *Metaphire* Sims & Easton, 1972 (and also to *Duplodicrodrilus* Blakemore, 2008 and *Manus* Blakemore, 2010) have been recurrently made in Japan. These attempts fail due to lack of basic knowledge of ICZN (1999) and have no merit. Nevertheless, an obligation is to again firmly quash continued assaults on ICZN's "standards, sense and stability" in universal zoological nomenclature.

Sims & Easton (1972) reviewed all the World's pheretimoid genera as then known and proposed placing the nominal taxon, genus *Pheretima*, subordinate to *Amynthas* that had been presumed to be invalidated by its alternative spelling as *Amyntas* – an objective homonym of *Amyntas* Wollaston, 1865 (Coleoptera).

Kinberg (1867) spelt the genus name *Amynthas* (p. 97) and *Amyntas* (p. 101); priority of the former spelling was confirmed by Sims & Easton (1972: 176) who considered Vaillant (1889: 62) the First Reviser establishing the validity of the spelling *Amynthas* over the second name that was preoccupied. Note too that *Amythas* Benham, 1921 (Polychaeta : Ampharetidae) – a monotypic genus for Antarctic *Amythas membranifera* Benham, 1921 – differs in having no "n".

Some recent workers have questioned whether the protocol used by Sims & Easton for restoration of a subsumed genus *Amynthas* was correct and conversely claim that the first to have mention the alternate spelling of *Amyntas* was Rosa (1888: 10). However, Rosa's work is not compliant with the current version of ICZN (1999: Article 24.2.3) for selection of correct original spellings that reads (with my bolding):

"If a name is spelled in more than one way in the original work, the first author to have cited them together and to have selected one spelling as correct is the First Reviser. The selected spelling (if not incorrect under Articles 32.4. or 32.5) is thereby fixed as the correct original spelling; any other spelling is incorrect (and therefore unavailable [Art. 32.4])."

This then requires citation of **both** alternate spellings of the genus name and selection of the one considered correct. Thus Rosa (1888) cannot be construed as the ICZN First Reviser. It is here confirmed that Sims & Easton (1972: 176) are seemingly justified (either by deliberation or prescient good fortune) under current ICZN (1999) about correct original spelling by their citing Vaillant (1889: 62) since this publication clearly mentioned both spellings (pages 48, 62, 63, 83, 84) and in [Errata](#), on page 296 noted that Kinberg spelt the name in two ways. But, by only correcting the table in which Vaillant (on p. 48) quotes Kinberg's work (as also on pp. 83 and 84) with *Amyntas* and NOT correcting his subsequent twice use (on pp. 62 and 63 in Vaillant's own table) of the alternative spelling "*Amynthas*", it may be taken that Vaillant (1889: 62) thereby fixed (whether intentionally or not) the alternative spelling "*Amynthas*" as the correct form of the name later adopted by Sims & Easton (1972: 176) and subsequently by these and most other authorities. Citation in an index of that publication (p. 298) is NOT a legitimate part of Vaillant's (1889) paper.

Although Michaelsen (1900) mentioned both forms as synonyms of *Pheretima*, without a need to choose which one he thought correct, it may well be that if it were not Vaillant (1889) being the First Reviser under current ICZN articles, it is conceivable that Sims & Easton (1972) were *de facto* ICZN official "First Revisers". In either case, in the 44 years since Sims & Easton (1972) restored and refined names there is a strong argument in favour of "*standards, sense and stability*". With such reasoning and with valid ICZN nomenclatural protocol for sustained progress, I herein endorse Sims & Easton's (1972) meticulous restoration of spelling *Amynthas* over *Amyntas* hereby ending debate about validity of the name and its priority over *Pheretima*, a non-Japanese genus typically separated morphologically, molecularly and geographically from both *Amynthas* and *Metaphire* (see also Blakemore, 2002; 2008; 2016b).

I also note (Blakemore, 2002; 2016b) that the type, *A. aeruginosus* (sic) Kinberg, 1867: 101, is particularly similar to *Amynthas taitensis* (Grube, 1866) and, if they eventually prove to be synonymous, the latter would apparently have date priority. This the more so since Kinberg's publication is here reconfirmed as 1867 not "1866".

Hebert *et al.* (2003) recognized that traditional "*taxonomic expertise is collapsing*"; moreover, Oláh *et al.* (2015) argue that it is already defunct and give several reasons why. In an era of lack of skill or support for such an already onerous science, is it really advisable to collapse a relatively stable taxonomy and waste yet more valuable time? I believe, on balance, there is no longer any need to ask ICZN Commissioners to rule on this issue of *Amynthas* validity.

Concerning male pores determination of *Amynthas*/*Metaphire*

Amynthas/*Metaphire* determination is straightforward when we have clear male pore differences such as in *Metaphire schmardae* (that has copulatory pouches with huge eversible 'air-bags' with glands and penes and that is now combined as *Duplodicrodrilus schmardae* (Horst, 1883) – the type of the new genus – see Blakemore, 2012b), but there are sometimes borderline cases that may be decided either way. I think the proper route to progress is to simply ask: "*Are the male pores superficial?*" (the

primitive/plesiomorphic state as incidentally found in *Amyntas*). If not, then they are “non-superficial”, i.e., apomorphic/derived as found in types of both *Metaphire* and *Pheretima* (see also Blakemore, 2010: 201) and, in further support for this reasoning, I quote Gates (1975: 7) on his opposite, confused and quite incorrect stance on this issue:

“Presence or absence of copulatory chambers is too vague. The really important character is whether the male pores are superficial or invaginate. In the latter case, whether in slight transverse slits of much deeper spaces still confined to the parietes or whether thick-walled copulatory chambers deeply penetrating into coelomic cavity.”

Gates (1982: 52) knew all about Sims & Easton’s (1972) revisionary work and the issue of *Amyntas/Metaphire* vs. *Pheretima*, but for ten years he deliberately ignored their proper scholarship to satisfy his own personal agenda. This questions his scientific integrity, and that of those who follow his mistaken taxonomy; plus his intellectual lucidity is also suspect in his attempt to classify male pores as invaginate vs. “non invaginate” (sic), as opposed to my simple and phylogenetically valid categories of “superficial vs. non-superficial” (Blakemore, 2000; 2013; 2016b). *Metaphire* Sims & Easton, 1972 is a genus of convenience, as its authors allowed (p. 171); but to dismiss it requires considerable courage and conviction or, at the very least, some better suggestion for which, to date, nobody has had such clarity of vision nor practical purpose to propose.

Regarding status of megadrile families Acanthodrilidae vs. Megascolecidae

While it is gratifying that Acanthodrilidae – rather than Acanthodrilinae – is being more widely accepted following my review (Blakemore, 2000), it seems remarkable that even after revisions by Blakemore (2003: 11, 2005, 2007b, 2013) it should still be necessary to explain how this family is separated on the basis of its male pores: viz., tautologically rather obvious acanthodriline vs. megascolecine in Acanthodrilidae vs. Megascolecidae, respectively; and NOT on their prostate form as per Gates (1959, 1972, 1982) and others. The ridiculous Gatesian system of tubular (misrepresented as “non-racemose”) vs. non-tubular seems to yet gain traction in some obscure, regional publications. According to this false system, species such as *Plutellus heteroporus* Perrier, 1873 (type of Plutellinae) and *Sebbius angus* (Blakemore, 1997), both with tubular prostates, would belong in Acanthodrilidae; and acanthodriline *Exxus wyensis* Gates, 1959 would be in Megascolecidae; which are clearly wrong on morphological, phylogenetic and molecular grounds (see Blakemore, 1994; 2013 and Fig. 4). Thus, to reiterate as simply as possible: while an acanthodriline Acanthodrilidae has only tubular forms, megascolecine Megascolecidae may have **either** tubular **or** non-tubular prostates. The acanthodriline families Octochaetidae, Benhamiidae & Exxidae all have meric nephridia, the latter uniquely developing non-tubular prostates (see Blakemore, 2000; 2007b; 2008; 2013).

A definitive example is cosmopolitan *Pontodrilus litoralis* (Pontodrilinae) as reviewed by Blakemore (2007a) and recently found as a new record in freshwater Taal Lake, Philippines (10th Nov., 2013, RJB) which has tubular prostates but is clearly not a member of any reasonable concept of Acanthodrilidae (see its barcode in Appendix 1).

In Fig. 4 preview phylotree, family allocation is confirmed with Acanthodrilidae (represented by *Microscolex dubius*) being separate and basal to all except Moniligastridae (*Drawida* spp.); while Ocnerodrilidae (*Eukerria saltensis*) is basal to all

Megascolecidae *s. strict* as per Michaelsen (1900) and Blakemore (2000; [2013](#)). Although COI gene is not best for family separation, further supporting examples are of three African Benhamiidae *Dichogaster spp.* found by the author in organic rice fields in 2013 – including *Di. saliens* (Beddard 1893) as a new Filipino record – with DNA of *Di. modigliani* (Rosa, 1896) published for the first time (Blakemore, [2016a](#): fig. 1; Genbank KT626582) differing from Acanthodrilidae *M. dubius* by >20% and from Australasian Octochaetidae *Deinodrilus orcus* Blakemore, [2013](#) from New Zealand by 18% (BLAST Identities are 510/639 = 80% and 520/633 = 82%, respectively).

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APPENDIX 1. mtDNA COI data & BLAST (<http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) with tree from iBOLD JET 2012 (<http://www.boldsystems.org/>)* – see Fig. 4.

>JET178-11 *Metaphire megascolidioides* – Lake Biwako specimen-1

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AACTCTATACTTCATTTTAGGAATCTGAGCTGGAATGATTGGGGCAGGAATAAGACTACTCATCCGAATTGAACTA
AGACAACCAGGTTTCATTCTTGGGGAGGGACCAACTATATAATACCATTGTAACAGCACACGCATTTCCTTATAATTT
TCTTTTTAGTAATGCCAGTATTTATTGGGGGATTGGAAATTGATTATTACCCCTAATACTAGGAACACCCGATATA
GCATTCCACGACTCAATAATATAAGATTTGACTACTCCCACCATCACTTATTCTTCTAGTATCCTCTGCTGCAGT
AGAAAAAGGAGCAGGAACAGGGTGAACAGTTTATCCTCCCCTAGCAAGAAATATTGCACACGCCGGTCCCTCAGT
AGACCTTGCAATCTTTTCACTACACCTTGCTGGTGATCATCAATTTTAGGAGCCATTAATTTTATTACCACAGTAA
TTAATATACGATGATCTGGACTTCGACTAGAACGAATCCCCTACTTCGCTGAGCAGTAGTGATTACAGTAGTACT
GCTATTACTTTCACCTCCAGTTCTGCGGGAGCTATTACAATACTGCTAACAGATCGAAACCTTAATACATCATTCT
TTGACCCCGCAGGTGGAGGAGACCAATCCTTTATCAACACCTGTTT
```

Genbank BLAST Results – 99% Genbank AB482107 from Kochi, Shikoku & AB542644 from Sapporo, Hokkaido, Japan; but just 92% AB536863 & AB542648 from Fukuoka, Kitakyushu. Difference of these Kyushu specimens of 8% indicate some specific divergence possibly meriting at least sub-specific status; but more work is required to confirm this. Korean specimens yet have no DNA barcodes to compare.
>JET179-11 *Metaphire megascolidioides* – Lake Biwako specimen-2, agrees 100%.

>WO39 *Pontodrilus litoralis* –Jeju 22nd May, 2012 RJB (cf. WO38 vagina mixup)**

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TACTTCATCCTAGGAGTATGAGCTGGGATAATTGGAGCTGGAATAAGACTACTTATTGCAATTGAACTAAGACAAC
CAGGAGCATTCTAGGGAGAGATCAACTATATAATACAATTGTTACTGCACACGCATTCTAATAATTTTTTCTTA
GTAATACCTGTATTTATTGGAGGATTTGGAACACTGATTACTACCCCTTATACTAGGAGCACCAGATATAGCTTTCC
ACGACTAAACAACATAAGATTTGACTTCTACCTCCTTCTAATCCTTCTAGTTTCATCAGCTGCAGTAGAAAAAG
GTGCAGGAACTGGATGAACAGTTTATCCACCATTAGCAAGTAATATTGCCCATGCTGGGCCATCAGTAGATCTAGC
CATTTTTTCACTACATTTAGCCGGGGCTTCATCAATTCTAGGAGCTATTAACCTTTATTACAACAGTTATTAATATAC
GATGATCAGGATTACGACTAGAACGAATTCCATTATTCGTATGGGCTGTAGTTATTACAGTAGTGCTACTACTATT
ATCCCTCCTGTGTAGCAGGGGCTATTACAATACTATTAACAGATCGCAATCTAAATACATCTTTCTTCGACCCAG
CAGGTGGGGGAGATCCA
```

Genbank BLAST agrees 99% with Genbank LC018735 *Pontodrilus litoralis* from Japan but just 87% for GU902107 specimen identified from “USA: coastal waters” & GU014012 an unidentified “*Megascolecidae* sp.” (sic). New records by the author of this species include for Taiwan in 2004, Galapagos Islands (e.g. Blakemore, 2006 - www.annelida.net/earthworm/Galapagos%20earthworms.pdf; 2007a); Jeju/Korea (Blakemore, 2013**), and now Lake Taal beach at Kanalakangan (‘Fallen Angel’) Resort as a new Filipino record (coll. RJB Nov., 2013 & RJB + RO Jan., 2014; samples in UPV: LP & R7 failed to yield DNA data due to UPV delay in sending tissue to genetics lab.). Affinity is with Megascolecidae rather than Acanthodrilidae.

DNA samples from species samples in Biwako Museum (collectors RJB + MN, 14-16.II.16) including Lumbricid *Bimastos parvus* (Eisen, 1874) as a **new record** from under rocks at Gushikawa Castle, Kumejima Island, Okinawa have yet to be sequenced.

*Note: ‘JET’ stands for my **Japanese Earthworm Types** project at iBOLD initiated after Nagoya COP10, courtesy of Dr Paul Hebert and team at Guelph Uni.

**Blakemore, R.J. (2013). Jeju-do earthworms (Oligochaeta: Megadrilacea) – Quelpart Island revisited. *Journal of Species Research*. 2(1): 15-54. [www.nibr.go.kr/eng/event/journal_spe_3_201302.jsp].

Fig. 4. Phylogenetic tree preview from iBOLD COI barcodes (<http://www.boldsystems.org/> JET project) with familial allocations and our taxon highlighted (actually darkened); the scale bar is 5% but >3% is often sufficient for specific separation in earthworms (Hebert *et al.*, 2003).

In Fig. 4, the genus *Metaphire* interlaces with genus *Amyntas* – as explained in text Discussion. Also note that *Amyntas* sp. [7-8] is now identified by BLAST as

Metaphire yamadai (Hatai, 1930) – see Blakemore (2012); *Amyntas* spp. [9-16 & 21-23] are all *A. cf. corticis* confirming a species-complex as identified by Blakemore (2013); *Heteropordrilus tryoni* from Closeburn/Samford, Qld in the author’s collection is the first sequence for this group of an Australian (and Indian?) “Plutelloid” (Plutellinae) cf. North American Argilophilinae (see Blakemore, 1994: 33; 2000; 2013); *Metaphire houlleti* spp-complex is described by Blakemore (2016a); *Metaphire cf. robustus* [24-27] = *Metaphire ryunome* Blakemore, 2012; *Amyntas cf. pingi* [30-33] are related to *A. carnosus* as determined by Blakemore (2012); *Amyntas* sp. [34] is *A. micronarius* (Goto & Hatai, 1899) according to BLAST (see Blakemore, 2012: 117); *Amyntas* sp. [35] still has no BLAST match and is itself possibly a sp. nov.; *Eisenia japonica* (Michaelsen, 1892) [47] is a topotype of this species-complex and [53] is now *E. j. hiramoto* Blakemore, 2012; but not shown are JET134 & 136-7 new sub-species *Eisenia japonica* “shiroatama” (unpublished) from Mishima. “*Drawida ashiuranoeri*” is another manuscript name that is likely synonymous with *D. japonica* (Michaelsen, 1892) – see Blakemore (2014). *Drawida hattamimizu* Hatai, 1930 neotype was definitively defined morphologically and molecularly by Blakemore *et al.* (2010) – the first time ever for an earthworm type.

Ocnerodrilid *Eukerria saltensis* seemingly sequenced for the first time (BLAST has no match) was a new Japanese record (see Blakemore *et al.*, 2006); acanthodrilid *Microscolex dubius* was a new Asian record (Blakemore, 2010; 2012); while a supposed “tubificid” [41-42] is now identified as Lumbriculidae type *Lumbriculus variegatus* (Müller, 1774) with JET-132 matching Genbank FJ639305 from Japan. This is an apparently new cosmopolitan record for Mishima (mature specimen Tokyo Museum An-470 col. RJB 16.III.2011) as the only published records I can find are in profundal lake habitats in northern Japan (viz. Ohtaka, 2014) although M.J. Grygier (pers. comm. July, 2016) says immature “*Lumbriculus*” sp. in LBM collection are recorded west of Lake Biwako. – See Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. *Lumbriculus variegatus* from EOL website (eol.org/pages/620776/overview c/o Malcolm Storey Creative Commons Licence); the JET-132-133 specimen is a new record of this cosmopolitan, exotic microdrile for Megumi spring, Mishima.

APPENDIX 2. Goto & Hatai earthworm sample jars from Tokyo Todai found at Yokohama YNU (author's preliminary report on discovery, October, 2010).

No.*	Labels (mostly Japanese)	Specimens	Condition	Type Status
Nil	Parasite (?) from the lung of a python. March, 1887	1 worm	Good	?
1	Nil	2 worms, lumbricids	dried	Non types
2	Nil	1 large worm	Dissected but in fair state	TYPE? (Possibly of <i>P. iizukai</i> ?)
3	Meiji 42 [= 1910]	Many worms	Good	Non types
4	Illegible	Worms?	Poor	?
5	Partly illegible “..COMMUNIS”	Microdriles	Fair	?
6	Partly illegible “Meiji 42”?	Worms	Dried/moldy	Non types?
7	Meiji 32 [1899] July 8, Formosa	Several	Wet	TYPES?
8	Meiji 32 [1899], location	Several	Dried	TYPES?
9	Meiji 32 [1899] July 3, location	Several	Good	TYPES?
10	Meiji 27 [1894] July.	5-6 of	Good	TYPES?
11	“20012 <i>Nais proboscides</i> O.F. Müller Naidomorpha, Oligochaeta. Leipzig”	Single	Good	?
12	Meiji 42 [1909] April, location	‘Soup’	Poor	Non types
13	Nil	Several	Fair, some dissected	?
14	Meiji 42 [1909], location	Many	Good	Non types
15	Nil	Many	Fair	Non types?
16	Illegible	Several	Dried	TYPES?
17	Meiji 42 [1909], location	Some	Fair	Non types
18	No date	One	Large undissected	?
19	Meiji 36 [1903]	Some	?	Non types
20	Meiji 36 [1903] December	Several	Good	Non types
21	Meiji 44 [1911] April 30, loc.	One	Good	Non type
22	Meiji 42 [1909] April 3, loc	One	Good	Non type
23	“ <i>Perichaeta in copula</i> May 27 1903 Tokyo”	Two	Fair	Non types
24	“ <i>Allolobophora foetida</i> Loc. Kofu, Kai”	Several	Fair	Non types
25	Illegible	Many	Fair (formalin)	TYPES?
26	“201 <i>Perichaeta communissima</i> Oligochaeta, Chaetopoda Tokyo”	Two	Good, one dissected	SYNTYPES
27	Meiji 33 [1890] June 9, location	Two	Fair, undissected	TYPES?
28	“Location (China)..., Prof. C. Ping.. <i>Perichaeta hupeiensis</i> Mich (?) Goto Oct 1924”	Some	Good	Non types
29	Meiji 42 [1899] April, location	Many	Moist, good	TYPES?
30	Nil	Many	Mixed polychaetes, coral and oligochaetes	Non types?
31	Nil	One lumbricid / criodrilid	Good	?
32	Meiji 42 [1904], location	Some	Fair	Non types
33	“ <i>Allolobophora foetida</i> Tokyo May 1 st 190...”	One	Good	Non type
34	“ <i>P. levis</i> Goto & Hatai Meiji 29 [1896] August [Location:]	Four specimens	Good, one dissected	SYNTYPES

	Kikkuchi, Kumamoto-ken. [Collector:] Takiyama”			
35	“ <i>Perichaeta micronaria</i> Tokyo”	One (in half)/two	Poor, dried	TOPOTYPE (or SYNTYPE?)
36	“ <i>Perichaeta micronaria</i> Meiji 29 [1896] August [Loc:] Tozaki, Kikkuchi, Kumamoto-ken. [Col:] Takiyama”	Several	Good	Probably not primary types as location not given in original description
37	“ <i>Bipalium</i> Saikyo... Kikuchi Summer of 1887 – 1889 90% Alcohol”	Many	Dried earthworms	Non types?
38	Meiji 42 [1909] April 5, loc.	Several	Fair	Non types
39	Meiji 37 [1904] “ <i>Eisenia sp.</i> ”	Many	Good	Non types
Nil (40?)	Label in Japanese	One earthworm	Good	Possibly of <i>P. megascolidioides</i> ?

* Code numbers are thought to have been stuck on jars by Mr Kotaro Ishizuka.

These vitally important historical samples now stabilized and stored under UMUTZ curatorial care of Dr Rei Ueshima with summary data presented in Blakemore & Ueshima (2011). No funding nor other support resources have yet been made available to me for completion of the descriptions of these classical type materials.